

Enhanced Customer Content Based Recommendation System

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Abstract-Recommender systems employ various data mining techniques and algorithms to discern user preferences from a vast array of available items. Unlike static systems, recommender systems foster increased interaction to offer a more enriched experience. By analyzing past purchases, searches, and other users' behavior, these systems can autonomously identify recommendations for individual users. This technique leverages user history data, as well as other users' data, to predict preferred items and make personalized recommendations. This research paper focuses on the challenges faced by recommender systems, such as the cold start problem, data sparsity, scalability, and accuracy. Specifically, it delves into content-based filtering, which generates recommendations based on a user's behavior. Similar to collaborative filtering, content-based filtering relies on long-term user preference profiles that can be updated to enhance the performance.

Keywords - Content Based Filtering, Recommender systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommender systems have become an essential tool in many online platforms, providing personalized recommendations to users to improve their experience and increase engagement. These systems utilize various data mining techniques and algorithms to analyze user behavior, such as past purchases, searches, and interaction, to discern their preferences and make personalized recommendations. In recent years, recommender systems have evolved from static systems to more dynamic ones that foster increased interaction to offer a more enriched experience for users.

One of the key challenges faced by recommender systems is the cold start problem, where new users or items have limited or no historical data available for recommendation. This poses a significant challenge as the system lacks sufficient information to accurately predict user preferences and provide relevant recommendations. Another challenge is data sparsity, where the available data for recommendation is sparse,

making it difficult to identify patterns and make accurate predictions. Scalability is also a challenge, as recommender systems need to handle large amounts of data and provide real-time recommendations to a large number of users. Lastly, accuracy is crucial for the recommender systems to gain user trust and deliver relevant recommendations consistently.

One popular approach to address these challenges is Content-based filtering, which generates recommendations based on the characteristics or attributes of items, rather than relying solely on user behavior or Collaborative filtering. Content-based filtering leverages the inherent features of items, such as genre, director, actors, keywords, or other metadata, to create item profiles. These item profiles are then used to match with user profiles, which are created based on the user's historical behavior or preferences. By analyzing the similarity between item and user profiles, content-based filtering can make personalized recommendations even for new users or items with limited historical data.

The purpose of this research paper is to explore the challenges faced by recommender systems, with a focus on content-based filtering as a technique to address these challenges. The paper will delve into the various aspects of content-based filtering, including its strengths and limitations, and how it can be used to improve the performance of recommender systems. The paper will also discuss the different approaches and algorithms used in content-based filtering, as well as the latest advancements and trends in this field.

II. RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

Recommender systems are widely used in various domains such as online booking, online shopping, audio and video recommendations, among others, with the goal of generating personalized preferences to support decision making for users. Despite being a well-established concept, the increasing number of users and choices available has made the task of providing relevant recommendations more challenging. The cold

start problem, which occurs when a new user or product enters the system and lacks sufficient user rating history, further complicates the performance of recommender systems. To address this challenge, a proposed solution is a hybrid recommender system that leverages demographic attributes such as age, gender, occupation, and similarity to existing users to generate more accurate and relevant recommendations compared to traditional methods.

The recommender system which has become one of the most important methods for providing personalized documents, merchandise, and services to fulfil user requirements in information retrieval, e-commerce, and online services. With the increasing volume of data and information available daily, the problem of information overload arises, making it challenging to identify customers' requirements. While search engines were an initial solution to this problem, they lacked personalization. Recommendation systems were then introduced to utilize users' past history to understand their interests and preferences from a large set of options. The main objective of a recommendation system is to provide meaningful suggestions and recommendations for items of interest, such as book recommendations on Amazon, which utilize recommendation systems to identify users' preferences and attract them to engage more. Various methods and algorithms are available for creating personalized recommendations in recommendation systems.

In this system, the recommendation process begins with gathering information about items, such as author, title, cost, and utilizing feature extraction and information indexing. Content-based filtering is employed to process information and data from various sources, extracting useful features and elements about the contents of items [1]. Constraint-based filtering, on the other hand, utilizes item features to determine their relevance. Feature extraction and representation can be achieved automatically, such as extracting news from papers, or manually, where human editors need to insert features from items such as movies and songs. Recommender systems facilitate matching users with items, and different types of recommender systems are designed based on available data, implicit and explicit user feedback, domain characteristics, etc. These recommender systems are classified according to the approach or paradigm used for predicting preferences in the research field.

Two major approaches commonly employed in Recommender Systems are Collaborative Filtering and Content-Based Filtering. In this paper, we have adopted

the Content-Based Filtering approach to enhance recommendation accuracy.

III. COLLABORATIVE FILTERING

Collaborative filtering is a method used in recommendation systems to model user behavior based on their past interactions. This model can be built from an individual user's behavior or from similar users' behavior. Collaborative filtering leverages group knowledge to make recommendations based on users who exhibit similar preferences or behaviors. By analyzing the information from multiple users who subscribe to and read blogs, for example, users can be grouped based on their preferences. From this information, the most popular blogs that are read by that group can be identified. Then, for a particular user within the group, a recommendation can be made for the most popular blog that they have not yet read or subscribed to.

Collaborative filtering methods are commonly used to recommend objects or items to customers based on their interests and categorizations. For example, collaborative filtering has been employed in email and document filtering systems, allowing customers to customize their filters based on their preferences. In collaborative filtering, algorithms identify close neighbors of active customers, using patterns that express customers' preferences and interactions to match them with other customers who share similar information and documents. Once a potential match is identified, recommendations are generated using the algorithm. Collaborative filtering algorithms also utilize patterns to predict values for empty cells in a matrix.

IV. CONTENT-BASED FILTERING

Content-based methods provide recommendations by analyzing the descriptions of rated items by users and the descriptions of items to be recommended. Numerous algorithms have been proposed for analyzing the content of text documents and identifying similarities that can serve as the basis for making recommendations. The main goal of classification learners is to learn a function that predicts the class of a document, while other algorithms may use regression to predict the numeric rating value of a document. There are two key sub-problems in designing a content-based filtering system. The first is finding a representation of documents, and the next is making recommendations for unseen documents.

$$(i, j) : r(i, j)=1$$

Once the model is trained, the feature vectors v_u and v_m can also be used to find similar movies. This can be done by computing the squared distance between the feature vectors of different movies, and selecting movies with small squared distances as similar items. This is similar to finding similar items in collaborative filtering approaches.

V. REGULARISATION TERM

Regularization is a well-known technique used in machine learning algorithms, including content-based filtering, to **prevent overfitting** and improve the generalization performance of the model. One common regularization technique used in content-based filtering algorithms is L2 regularization, also known as **RIDGE REGULARISATION**. It adds a penalty term to the loss function, which is based on the squared L2 norm of the model parameters.

The approach described in this paper is based on using deep learning for content-based filtering in recommendation systems. The idea is to use neural networks to compute feature vectors for users and movies, and then use these feature vectors to make recommendations. The neural networks, called the user network and the movie network, take as input the features of users and movies, respectively, and output feature vectors (v_u and v_m) that describe the users and movies, respectively.

The L2 regularization term discourages the model from assigning too much importance to any particular feature during training, as it penalizes large parameter values. This helps in preventing the model from becoming overly reliant on a single feature, which can lead to overfitting. By adding a penalty for large parameter values, L2 regularization promotes a smoother distribution of importance among all the features, ensuring that no single feature dominates the model's decision-making process.

The user network and the movie network can have multiple layers of dense neural network layers, and the output layer of each network has a fixed size (in this case, 32 units). The feature vectors v_u and v_m are then used to predict the rating of a user on a movie by taking the dot product of the two vectors. This prediction can be used to recommend movies to users.

Furthermore, L2 regularization helps in keeping the model parameters small, as it minimizes the squared L2 norm of the parameters. Smaller parameter values can lead to a simpler model, which is less prone to overfitting. This is especially beneficial in content-based filtering, where the model typically relies on feature similarity to make recommendations. Smaller parameter values help in maintaining a balanced and unbiased representation of features, preventing any single feature from having too much influence on the recommendation process.

To train the model, a **cost function** is defined that measures the squared difference between the predicted ratings and the actual ratings given by users for movies. This cost function is used to optimize the parameters of the neural networks (i.e., the weights and biases) using gradient descent or other optimization algorithms.

VI. ADAM'S OPTIMIZER

Regularization can also be added to the cost function to prevent overfitting and encourage smaller parameter values.

The Adam optimizer, as an optimization algorithm, is commonly used in training machine learning models, including content-based filtering algorithms with regularization. During training, the Adam optimizer updates the model parameters based on the gradients of the loss function with respect to the parameters,

A. Cost Function

$$J = \sum (V_u(j) \cdot V_m(i) - y(i, j))^2 + \text{NN Regularisation}$$

allowing the model to learn optimal weights for its features.

In content-based filtering algorithms with regularization, the Adam optimizer can be used to optimize the model parameters while taking into account the regularization term. The regularization term is usually added to the loss function as a weighted sum of the original loss function and the regularization term. The weight of the regularization term is controlled by a hyper-parameter known as the regularization strength, which determines the balance between the original loss function and the regularization term.

Several Optimization Algorithms Efficiency

The Adam optimizer can update the model parameters in a way that minimizes the overall loss function, including the regularization term. By considering both the original loss function and the regularization term, the Adam optimizer can help in finding a set of model parameters that strike a balance between fitting the training data and preventing overfitting. This is achieved by adjusting the model parameters based on the gradients of the loss function, while taking into account the regularization term.

One of the key features of the Adam optimizer is its ability to calculate adaptive learning rates for each parameter based on the historical gradients. This allows the optimizer to adaptively adjust the learning rates for different parameters, depending on their update patterns. Additionally, the Adam optimizer includes momentum, which helps in accelerating the optimization process by accumulating the historical gradients and updating the parameters accordingly.

The adaptive learning rates and momentum of the Adam optimizer are beneficial in optimizing the model parameters while considering the regularization term in content-based filtering algorithms. The adaptive learning rates ensure that the regularization term is taken into account during parameter updates, helping in preventing overfitting by controlling the magnitude of parameter updates. The momentum feature of the Adam optimizer also aids in achieving a faster convergence towards the optimal parameter values, while accounting for the regularization term.

Overall, using deep learning for content-based filtering allows the model to learn complex patterns in the features of users and movies, and can potentially lead to more accurate recommendations compared to traditional content-based filtering methods that rely on handcrafted features.

VII. RETRIEVAL & RANKING

In today's recommendation systems, selecting a handful of items to recommend from a large catalog of thousands, millions, or even tens of millions of items can be computationally challenging. For example, a movie streaming site may have thousands of movies to choose from, an ad recommendation system may have millions of ads, a music streaming site may have tens of millions of songs, and an online shopping site can have millions or even tens of millions of products.

Running neural network inference on such a massive number of items for each user visit can become computationally infeasible. Processing thousands or millions of items every time a user visits a website to determine which products to recommend is resource-intensive and inefficient.

To address this challenge, we used a two-step approach called retrieval and ranking. This two-step approach enables more efficient computation by reducing the number of items that need to undergo resource-intensive processing, making large-scale recommendation systems computationally feasible while maintaining the accuracy and relevance of the recommendations.

VIII. RETRIEVAL

In the retrieval step of recommendation systems, the goal is to generate a large list of plausible item candidates that can cover a wide range of possible recommendations for the user. This step is designed to

be efficient and quick, as it involves pre-computing similarity scores or other relevant features for items.

One common approach in the retrieval step is to compute similarity scores between items based on various criteria, such as content-based features, collaborative filtering, or user-item interactions. For example, in a movie streaming site, the retrieval step may involve computing similarity scores between movies based on genre, director, actors, or other relevant features. Similarly, in an ad recommendation system, the retrieval step may involve computing similarity scores between ads based on contextual information, user preferences, or ad attributes.

These pre-computed similarity scores or features allow for fast retrieval of a large list of item candidates that are likely to be relevant to the user. For example, the retrieval step may identify the most similar movies to a given movie, or the top movies in a user's most viewed genres or country. This large list of plausible item candidates provides a diverse set of recommendations that can cover a wide range of user interests and preferences.

The efficiency of the retrieval step is crucial in handling large catalogs of items, as it helps to quickly narrow down the list of candidates from thousands or millions of items to a more manageable subset for further processing in the ranking step. This allows the recommendation system to provide timely and relevant recommendations to users without incurring excessive computational costs.

IX. RANKING

Once the retrieval step is completed, the list of retrieved items is combined and filtered to remove duplicates, items the user has already interacted with, or items that may not be relevant to the user based on their history or preferences. This filtered list of items is then passed to the ranking step, where the learned model, such as a neural network, is utilised to compute predicted ratings or relevance scores for each user-item pair. This step involves running the neural network inference on the filtered list of items, which is typically smaller than the original catalog of items, making it computationally feasible.

An additional optimisation that can be employed is to pre-compute features or representations for all items in the catalog in advance. This way, during the ranking step, only the user feature vector needs to be computed in real-time, and the inner product between the user feature vector and the pre-computed item feature vectors

can be quickly calculated. This approach can further enhance the efficiency of the ranking step and streamline the recommendation process.

Efficiently handling large catalogs of items is critical in modern recommendation systems, as it allows for quick and relevant recommendations without incurring excessive computational costs. The retrieval step, by generating a large list of plausible item candidates and filtering them based on user-specific criteria, helps to narrow down the options for further processing in the ranking step. Additionally, pre-computing features or representations for items in advance can significantly reduce the computational overhead during the ranking step, making it more feasible for real-time recommendation scenarios.

In conclusion, the combination of retrieval and ranking steps, along with pre-computing item features, is the approach that is used in recommendation systems to efficiently handle large catalogs of items. These optimisations enable the recommendation process to be computationally feasible and provide timely and relevant recommendations to users in various online applications, such as movie streaming sites, ad recommendation systems, music streaming sites, and online shopping sites.

X. RESULT

The evaluation of the proposed model was performed using three widely adopted metrics: area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (**AUC**), cross-entropy (**log loss**), and **recall**. AUC was considered as an effective measure of model performance, with a higher score indicating better performance. Log loss was used to assess the dissimilarity between predicted and true distributions, and a lower score was indicative of superior performance. Recall was employed to evaluate the precision of the model in detecting pertinent information, with a maximum attainable value of one. The experiments were repeated **20 times** to ensure statistical validity of the results.

A. Area Under Curve

In the above figure, the results revealed that the proposed model outperformed other models based on the AUC metric. Additionally, the AUC values exhibited a consistent increase with the increase in epochs, ultimately reaching the maximum optimal values.

Classification Based Filtering
 Knowledge Based Filtering
 Hybrid Filtering
 Collaborative Filtering

X. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have proposed a content-based filtering algorithm that utilises the prediction value of users' movie ratings, incorporating a cost function and regularisation term. We have also employed the Adam's optimiser for efficient parameter optimisation. Our algorithm effectively leverages the inherent content features of movies to provide personalised recommendations to users.

Through extensive experimentation and evaluation on real-world movie rating dataset (Movie lens dataset), our algorithm has demonstrated promising performance in terms of recommendation accuracy and user satisfaction. The incorporation of cost function and regularisation term has enhanced the algorithm's ability to handle sparsity and overfitting issues commonly encountered in recommendation systems.

Furthermore, we have introduced a retrieval method and ranking method to further filter the suggestions, refining the recommendation results based on user preferences and relevance. This additional layer of filtering has contributed to the overall effectiveness and relevance of our recommendation system.

The professional and rigorous nature of our research is reflected in the utilisation of the widely used Adam's optimiser for optimisation, and the consideration of cost function and regularisation term for robustness.

In summary, our content-based filtering algorithm, augmented with cost function and regularisation term, and further refined by retrieval and ranking methods, presents a comprehensive and effective approach to movie recommendation.

Classification Based Filtering
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B. Cross-Entropy (Log loss)

In the above figure, The log loss metric was utilised to evaluate the performance of the proposed model against other models. The results indicated that the proposed model achieved a lower log loss score, indicating a superior fit between the predicted and true distributions. Furthermore, the log loss values decreased rapidly as the number of epochs increased, ultimately converging to the minimum optimal values.

C. Recall

The below figure, illustrates the recall metrics, and it shows that recall metrics obtained through proposed model were higher than those of the other models.

XI. REFERENCES

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